

Digitalization made IT essential for a working society. Europe needs to define and defend its digital essentials for sovereignty.

Europe's need for digital essentials, individual sovereignty and consumer protection

By THOMAS HOBERG

Information technology (IT) is now critical to a functional society and should be treated as such. The spread of digitalization across the globe has created new power structures, ruled over by technology monopolies. Perhaps more profoundly, the digitalization of global interaction has brought humanity into a contact that is far too close, immediate and unfiltered for comfort. Without the support of a spatiality¹ which allows us to reuse the social code of civilization and diplomacy learned through centuries, very much based on distance and visibility, we enter a phase where basic civility needs to be relearned, while our ability to inflict annoyance, anger or outright harm has been greatly enhanced.

This article explores some of the trends towards a digital chasm. It outlines some of the key issues in terms of platform power, vendor lock-in, and digital essentials, and suggests ways in which Europe can reclaim sovereignty over its participation in the digital sphere.

Key insights

- Digitalization has made IT become globally essential and critical, causing the underlying rifts in political values to widen and split. Political battle lines are currently drawn across supply chains and trenches spring up in software, and there is no sign of reversal of this new digital chasm.
- National governments, legislation, courts and plebiscites, who intrinsically have only a local mandate, can suddenly have a global impact, cause disruption or even completely cut off other nations and regions, merely because of where an essential piece of software was created or a where a critical service is operated. This risk is hardly even evaluated, let alone managed.

- The mere existence of open-source solutions or alternatives is not enough to compensate that risk, because they need continued maintenance and evolution.
- Peddlers of some niche products² in quirky emerging markets have turned into global cloud giants that mediate nearly every significant transaction between people and businesses, and try to shoehorn their terms-of-purchase into constitutions of a platform or metaverse they believe they own, selling often only an illusion of ownership in return for digital indenture.
- Digital platforms have grown from shopping malls into omnidirectionally integrated digital giants that challenge sovereign nations simply by force of economic gravity and transactional reach. Peaceful coexistence is impossible beyond a certain size; sovereigns need to act decisively.

¹ See the "Gaming, content and the metaverse" article in this HiPEAC Vision.

² A mobile digital music player using digital rights management (DRM) to control content distribution without physical media – the Apple iPod that morphed into the iPhone later.

Key recommendations

- The ability to survive in a strongly partitioned internet depends on the ability to take control, create a local fork and maintain software digital essentials at the required quality. It means that the EU cannot wait for such software access partitioning to happen; it needs to sponsor a fully capable developer community within Europe for all digital essentials today, ready to fork in case of a partition, but also ready to rejoin once conflicts has been resolved.
- Europe needs to foster the creation of new digital essentials, especially in open source and around enabling smart digital assistants that are loyal, support multi-compliance and enhance privacy, which can be used as division busters and bargaining chips for re-merging. Most attractive may be alternatives to proprietary (e.g. Office) or control-locked (Android) offerings.
- Platform power is generated by retaining control beyond "purchase" and trying to force consumers into subscriptions. Any control beyond purchase³ must be broken via regulation and a

full purchase with or without support must be made available at a reasonable price.

- The roles of a device vendor, software vendor, mall operator, gaming server provider, digital asset notary etc. must be segregated cleanly and completely to ensure that consumers cannot be blackmailed, and independent merchants be abused. That segregation may not just have to be functionally, but also geographically to ensure that functionality and services can be maintained in the EU, when a new digital division opens up and even if such a segregation isn't required or even prohibited in a merchant's/publisher's home market.
- Mandate very strong protections for individual sovereignty of personal computing device owners, right-to-repair and the de-coupling of devices from vendors without losing current functionality. Break vendor lock-in on software shops, mandate software quality control and insurance (against malware, viruses), potentially at distinct levels on shop operators much like food safety⁴.

Global digital divisions

While the internet might have taken the world by storm, digitalization today also storms the internet. Yes, the internet may have lowered, even levelled, some barriers,

just as travel, the printing press, radio and television did. But when the majority of all interpersonal business and communication is transacted on the internet, all the remaining cultural and political divisions

will follow and mirror the complexities of social and political graphs in cyberspace.

The tale of a truly open and neutral cyberspace is at best a pipe dream, more

The Berlin Wall (source: Andreas Prott on Adobe Stock). Today, geopolitical divisions are often manifested in the "digital chasm".

³ DRM requirements may require enforcement support.

⁴ Which is certainly not failsafe, but probably better than having none.

likely an attempt to exhaust a technology lead before regulation catches up.

The internet was about objective science and technology at its beginning, where opinions and beliefs seem to matter less. It is mostly about content today, where values and culture are very subjective and local.

Trade has often resolved conflicts of interest very in human history because war is terribly expensive. But when interests can no longer be balanced via exchanges, trenches spring up. On the internet this may still seem recent, even if the Great Firewall was built only three years after the internet arrived in China 1994[1].

We still think that everything on the internet is immediately available, and disturbances a technical problem that will be resolved quickly. When the world is conflicted and when even within Europe fragmentation seems on the rise, we need to plan and prepare not just for cyberwar, which already has become as ubiquitous as cybercrime, but for a highly variable multitude of much deeper divisions, some of which may last a long time.

The supply-chain issues which have gained significant attention over the last years are only a hint of what is to follow in terms of internet content and services, including some of the very basic and early ones, which seem rather technical and should therefore provoke little debate.

While there has been some attention on supply chains for raw materials, foodstuff, and hardware, we may be much too careless about the software and services, especially where open-source code, free services or content are concerned.

We came very close to a coup d'état in the United States on 6 January 2021, where a person was grasping for power that likes to dip its fingers directly into the dearest secrets of any person or nation state from his private estate. We also live in a world where a few people on the US Supreme Court feel no compunction about holding the bodies of half their own population hostage, so it is safe to assume they feel

even fewer compunctions to impose their whim on everyone else on the planet.

The dominance of US hyper-scalers over the internet in its current form means that US presidents and courts can seize, stop, hijack, infiltrate, abuse pretty near all of it, at will or the drop of a gavel. Even if Microsoft, Amazon, Google, Meta, and the various other internet giants consider themselves truly global and maintain the physical assets of their clouds very close to their global client base, they can't but bow to the ultimate authorities back home, wherever they operate. In that regard they are no different to Chinese or Russian companies; nor in fact could a European company free itself from EU regulation just because parts of it operate elsewhere.

In October 2022, the so-called “Bureau of Industry and Security”, an office inside the US Department of Commerce, unilaterally decided to cut off China's semiconductor industry from nearly every relevant supplier and customer on the planet. They did not ask or consult the European Union, Japan, South Korea, Israel or any other nation heavily invested in the international chip industry, nor the global customer base. The UNO was not involved, neither was the World Trade Organization or any lesser international body[2]. An under-secretary of the US government assumed control over the global chips industry because the US believe their historical lead

in that industry not only entitles them to this power, but that this lead should also be maintained at a point when China is at the verge of overtaking. They did so secure in the knowledge that without US-controlled technology a full range and stack of IT products cannot be created. But they also chose to ignore that without many global players outside the US, it is similarly handicapped itself.

If Europe could rest assured that the United States would treat it with “near domestic” privileges and would remain its staunch ally in the pursuit of democracy and human rights against totalitarian regimes in mainland China, Russia and North Korea, such initiatives eventually might even find political support, especially when asked politely. But blind faith into the United States as a pillar of democracy and an intimate friend of Europe has obviously become misplaced. The United States have declared the equivalent of a digital cold war on China, but as a hardly noticed collateral they have filed for a digital divorce with Europe, choosing “America First”. Instead of negotiating, the US government seems to have adopted the “disruption religion”, which according to Peter Thiel[3], one of its main proponents, regards democracy as incompatible with freedom.

No one outside the United States, no person, no enterprise, and no government may ignore that they are at the whim of

5 Including Microsoft Edge.

powers completely outside their control. To do so, after the events of the last years, can't be anything but grossly negligent. This must be changed quickly, decisively, and with regulatory support, because otherwise in many cases such sudden and drastic changes would violate contract law.

Digital essentials for Europe

Few things are as important to the IT industry as economy of scale. Whether it's software code or a hardware description language, creating truly original lines of code is extraordinarily expensive and those high costs can only be offset by maximum reuse and deployment at maximum scale, preferably global. This naturally leads to code monoculture, because maintaining more than one code base for the same functionality adds cost without apparent benefit.

Industry giants use this effect to create effective monopolies and lock-in effects even if there is no purchase price involved by sponsoring open-source code projects or free services. Perhaps the best-known example currently is Google's Chrome browser, which together with all its derivatives dominates the browser market everywhere outside the Apple universe. A broken or unavailable Chrome nearly breaks the Internet, which is why the EU must guarantee the free availability of such digital essentials, independent of any other political bloc, in case of a political rupture, a cyber-war or physical conflict that could last years.

It is a move that has been similarly anticipated and undertaken by political blocs which are further away from the US than Europe e.g. North Korea, Russia and China for the same purpose of ensuring a minimal degree of digital autonomy.

While it is easier to maintain software digital essentials than to produce a full stack of hardware locally, it is not enough to just mandate the use of open-source code. **The ability to survive in a strongly partitioned internet depends on the ability to take control, create a local fork and maintain software digital essentials at the required quality. It means that the EU cannot wait for such software access**

partition to happen; it needs to sponsor a fully capable developer community within Europe for all digital essentials today, ready to fork in case of a partition, but also ready to rejoin once a conflict has been resolved.

Compared to the number of public employees currently involved in the maintenance and evolution of our societies cultural and legal code (e.g. teachers and all branches of government), those required to maintain our societies software base would be miniscule, yet their importance is difficult to overrate. Just imagine Europe were to lose some or all of the digital essentials listed in the box.⁶

1. a Linux distribution for
 - a) PCs, b) servers, c) mobiles,
 - d) IoT/embedded (e.g. Debian[4])
2. an Android fork[5] for tablets and phones, a Chromium fork for "Chromebooks"
3. a hypervisor (unless included in 1.[6])
4. a browser (e.g. Firefox[7])
5. an office suite (e.g. Libreoffice[8])
6. a team collaboration suite including conferencing (e.g. NextCloud[9])
7. an e-reader (PDF & book formats e.g. SumatraPDF[10])
8. a multimedia player (e.g. VLC[11])
9. mail clients/server unless included in 4[12].
10. a firewall/content-filter appliance (not necessarily as a separate image but included in 1. or in a container) e.g. OpenSense[13]
11. a messaging server and client platform (e.g. Signal[14])
12. thin-client/remote access tools[15]
13. VPN tools[16]
14. a compiler (e.g. GCC/LLVM)
15. an IDE
16. code repository tools (e.g. GitLab)
17. archiver (zip)
18. a Wikipedia
19. a search engine
20. DNS/PKI/CERT

How the EU ensures these assets and capabilities will remain available without restrictions in case of a partition from a major part of these software communities needs to be worked out and the approach may differ and change between them. Prescribing the use of such open-source essentials over proprietary solutions from outside vendors wherever the government is in direct control (that includes education), would be a much-needed start, especially since companies like Microsoft tend to sponsor deployments of Office 365 in those very same populations to deprive open-source alternatives like Libreoffice[17] and Nextcloud[18] of growth opportunities[19]. EU sovereignty can't bow to the lowest bidder, especially one that makes EU citizen private data available for corporate and US government abuse by design.

The economic threat from the cloud giants

Cloud computing has generated huge scale-benefit profits, which hyper-scalers have invested into bespoke solutions for all use cases that aggregated into sufficient mass.

For those solutions they have transitioned over the last ten years from custom software on commodity hardware to tailor-made everything, all parts of data centre infrastructure to proprietary chips, chassis, fabrics and software stacks, none of which are typically available to competitors, with the exception of the Open Compute Project (OCP)[20].

Corporate IT and smaller IT service providers can no longer compete, because they cannot purchase the ingredients that would level the field. Facebook's OCP was an attempt to enable a level field, because Facebook itself did not want to be forced into a competitor's cloud. But they are also losing that battle, and are becoming too small against what Amazon can do while facing rough headwinds from all directions.

Today only China has tried to out-scale the US technology giants, but the US technology sanctions currently seem to steer

⁶ Please note that curating this list is the first action to take.

China towards profiting from its greatest asset: the size and growth perspective of its domestic market protected from US competition.

IT is naturally global. Without restrictions, every service, even the most popular or critical, consolidates to a minimal number of providers, even a single one.

Europe needs such essential services, either some that are uniquely European or others protected against global competition while they incubate. Privacy and democracy are currently the only ones that seem scarce in the US, China, Russia, and other large parts of the world with less disposable income. If Europe can't utilize this or find others, it can only become a niche presence in global IT.

The personal computing space

We tend to regard (personal) computing devices as a single “thing”, and apply a single set of rules to them, including all their external communications.

That is no longer how we use them, and it creates unsolvable problems both for sovereignty of individuals or civil collectives, and for governments or other regulators who need to be able to wield executive power to remain sovereign.

The current executive overreach into encrypted messengers and on-device scanning for “harmful content” risk criminal and executive abuse and expose device owners to harm. Yet the demand for total “privacy” for both these devices and all their communication effectively eliminates executive power in a fully digitalized world and results in anarchy.

We need to create differentiations and discriminations which currently do not exist, mostly because the device vendors and internet giants are profiting from an effective executive monopoly, acting as pseudo governments, or creating metaverses as regulatory exclaves from our ground universe.

These vendor “dictatorships” have been going on for more than a decade now, so they have fully exploited any “move fast and break things”-innovation sprints one might grant to juveniles; there is no excuse to further delay taking the reins of absolute power from mature industries big enough to cower smaller nations. China and other totalitarian regimes are completely right to understand the necessity; the EU and other democracies urgently need to develop matching frameworks, legal and technical.

We need to distinguish between **activities/apps**, who often act as agents of proxies not just of the owner, but for others (e-government/health, employers, even service providers), distinct **pools of data** these may need to maintain separately and securely and then **communications**, both external but also internally within the device.

Recommendations to support individual sovereignty

1. A personal computer (which includes all smartphones, tablets, chromebooks etc.) is *personal*, the owner the only true sovereign. A manufacturer has no right to restrict an owner's rights as to the software and services he runs on them. Any software that acts against the interest of the owner is illegal by default, especially when it does so unbeknownst to the computer owner, grossly so after the interest against it has been expressed⁷.
2. Devices, software, and services sold in the EU need to comply with EU law and require an EU legal entity that can be held responsible, penalized for non-compliance, and sued for damages from within the EU. Bigger, more critical services require the same at country level; they also need a regional fallback service to ensure continuity and easy consumer protection⁸.
3. Consumers must be given a choice to manage their computing devices on their own (“rooting”), or delegate management authority to a provider of their choice (not just the vendors like Apple, Google, and Microsoft).

4. Computing devices need to support enclaves, software partitions or embassies in such a way that personal, employer, e-health, e-government, and service provider applications can run in an environment that protects these apps and their data from any other, including the device owner (to enable digital rights management), who retains “traffic control” (not content control) over apps and data. That traffic control must include the ability to freeze, back up, remove and restore (encrypted) enclaves to manage contractual changes or international travel.
5. **We recommend that the EU fund research in proper international enclave management, as this topic is not sufficiently explored, to put in full practice with consumers travelling across bigger borders.**
6. Personal computers must have either an open-source or open application programming interface (API) base firmware, so owners can choose or write their own operating systems.
7. Any operating system sold with the device needs to continue to work, and do so with support from within the EU, if a political or environmental crisis erupts at or beyond EU borders.
8. Firmware that is no longer maintained by the vendor must be verified to contain no exploitable vulnerabilities from their APIs or open sourced for a minimum of ten years after stop of sales. Vendors must set up matching escrow services for devices sold in Europe.
9. There must be no apps already pre-installed on computers. Install-ready images can be provided on the device but need to be removable easily. No vendor may prescribe the use of a particular variant of a generic app for generic service or document type e.g. Edge- or Safari-browsers, PDFs or office documents, video or audio files, conferencing or remote connections.
10. **Service providers and software vendors may need to be regulated similar to food safety or building codes.** Yes, the safety of software is a bit more difficult to assess than testing the stability of

⁷ When internet users send “do not track”, that is a very clear declaration of will, which may be ignored without penalty.

⁸ Really free and open-source software will require special attention, software that's only free to start and then commercialized via subscriptions or in-app purchases needs to be regulated similar to a purchase.

concrete, but the industry is developing methods and frameworks, a state of the art that is evolving much like building codes or food-safety regulations are not static. And like those they need not be entirely government operated, while they certainly need to be strictly split between vendors, underwriters, the creators and the monitors of the processes. The effort manufacturers are currently investing can certainly be replicated and perhaps improved within the EU and in accordance with the privileges applications demand and the context or enclave in which they run: there is less need to check for GDPR compliance in a game that runs in an enclave securely kept free from any personal data. The IT software industry and even PCs, mobile devices, the IoT and the cloud have come of age and grown far too big to be treated like kids: the gloves need to come off. Safety, security and compliance are in the public interest and a sovereign mandate in a digital society. Note that unfettered “innovation” in steam boilers also had to be reined in, once they spread too widely to ignore their potential harm. And just like you cannot rely on used-cars salesmen to run road safety inspections, the major technology companies cannot remain in sole charge for developing app safety guidelines and their execution on the devices they sell.

- 11.No firmware, operating system or app may send telemetry, usage, or personal data without the owner’s informed consent; the initial setting must always be deactivated. The only exception is digital rights management at reasonable granularity (e.g. once every six months). That data format must be documented and inspectable. “Embedded” browsers or viewers must follow the user preference determined before first use.
- 12.“Do not track” must be respected; ignoring it must be made a criminal offence. Research into creating a variant that works should be funded by the EU.
- 13.Code injection by apps into websites must be illegal, selective code execution (and content filtering e.g. for ad protection) from websites an unalienable right: copyright on code may not beat ownership of the execution environment.

14.Content filters searching e.g. for child pornography, blasphemy or content judged politically incorrect may not be performed on data at rest within the private enclave without previous consent. The owner must be given the ability to delete or quarantine incompliant data without triggering outside communication (“spying on the owner”). Local legal, corporate or vendor ethical rules should only be applied to data that is being moved between enclaves or transmitted on public networks (which really is just another enclave).

- 15.We need to support a facility by which e.g. family members can exchange data privately between themselves, that might be judged incompliant for more public transmission, e.g. parents exchanging pictures or videos of their babies bathing.
- 16.Disconnecting digital service for incompliance must be contestable in a local court [21].
- 17.No computer must require an internet connection or the registration of an owner to operate as purchased, with the installed operating system or provided applications.
- 18.No app or service may be withheld from an individuum that does not want to be identified if it’s not necessary to function for the consumer. A vendor’s interest in “improving our services” is not a necessity.

Consumer protection

In a mostly digital industry with few physical assets, horizontal expansion is at the heart of the software revolution and cloudification. But verticalization also has both a much lower investment hurdle and higher incentives for control, speed to market and cost savings. It helps keep out the competition as well, to the point where every content provider, from device vendors like Apple or Sony to social network providers like Meta and game publishers like Tencent is aiming to create their own walled garden metaverse, using the Amazon approach of providing a business platform that “compe-kills” its more successful customers via the upper hand built into the base.

These big players then seek to protect their near total control of these captive

markets by claiming that governmental regulation would stifle innovation and their ability to create “disruptive new products” But after their initial transformative idea, all their remaining innovation is the smokescreens thrown up to keep the regulators out. Underneath are business practices similar to the ones that J.D. Rockefeller employed 150 years ago, and the very reason anti-trust legislation was invented. These metaverses are little more than the attempt to invent a private ethos and evade ground rules, a rather ancient technique also employed by the mafias and triads for centuries.

They rely on rapid addition of features and services to keep ahead of regulation and control, which today tends to wait for the first complaints to start investigating. By the time they might have won an anti-trust case, starved-off competitors have fallen to the wayside, because the legal system operates far too slowly for a digital society.

That is why regulation must anticipate the vertical and horizontal integration and walling of metaverse gardens and reverse the liability for proving competitive good behaviour. Vendors and service providers need to prove how the market remains open to competition, while breakup along verticals, horizontals and perhaps across value system borders need to be automatic once a threshold of significance is achieved.

This reversal of proof is also necessary and important in other areas cited below.

Malls vs merchants

For a couple of decades towards the end of the last century, large shopping malls dominated retail. Much like an apartment building, malls provided central services like parking, security, power and water supplies, ventilation/heating/air-conditioning, waste disposal, perhaps even delivery services to shop owners who could rent out space for their business.

Mall owners/operators and merchants – in their role as mall consumers – were separate and would not compete with one another, as that would give any shop owned or operated by a mall owner an unfair advantage over other merchants.

Amazon, Apple, Google, Microsoft, Steam today operate digital malls, but they also compete with merchants as their customers within those malls. And that competition is rather lopsided and far too easy to exploit e.g. by Amazon, who have an extraordinary amount of insight into the business of any merchant using their platform and can use that knowledge to replace them.

Steam[22] is mostly seen as a game distribution platform today but started as an internal patch and update service for Valve as a publisher. It gained quick popularity and dominates the PC games market because it eliminated the copy protection worries of publishers and de-materialized distribution e.g. via CD/DVD media with the help of a reliable digital rights management (DRM) platform. Consumers let go of purchasing physical media with the understanding that Steam would safeguard what they bought and enable them to re-install or move any game they owned to any device they operated. For that combination of a working DRM and consumer convenience Steam charges 30% “service tax”, generating revenue that far outstrips Valve’s earning as a publisher.

But it has also sparked the envy of the largest game publishers, as well as those companies who believe they retain ownership over the platform they sell devices or software for like Apple or Microsoft.

The roles of a device vendor, software vendor, mall operator, gaming server provider, digital asset notary etc. must be segregated cleanly and completely to ensure that consumers cannot be blackmailed, and independent merchants be abused. That segregation may not just have to be functionally, but also geographically to ensure that functionality and services can be maintained in the EU, when a new digital divide opens up and even if such a segregation isn’t required or even prohibited in a merchant’s/publisher’s home market.

The game server and digital asset notary functions also need to be segregated out to ensure that the purchased digital assets remain functional even if the original publisher has ceased operations.

In short: dematerialization enforced by the publishers of any digital content may not result in compromised ownership.

Purchase rights and ownership of digital content

1. A purchase transfers ownership over a digital copy. A limited use “purchase” or revocable content may not be labelled as “purchase”.
2. The copy may be watermarked or branded to reflect the purchaser and the copyright expiry and DRM can be used with accordance to restrictions (e.g. multiple concurrent devices) clearly stated at the time of purchase.
3. Any content without copyright, even if purchased, must not be distributed with DRM.
4. Any purchased content that runs out of copyright must be de-protectable by the owner. A service or tool must be provided for ten years after purchase.
5. Any purchased content under copyright needs to be kept available for download for as long as specified during sale.

Addiction

Computer and console gaming originally depended on selling physical media (ROM cartridges, CDs, DVDs) for monetization, which was tailored to affluent Western markets where consumers could afford to own computers and game consoles.

In Asia, most gamers could not afford their own computers but went to internet cafés instead, where for an hourly fee they could play games that were either pirated outright or re-implemented as clones.

Internet cafés enable new business models based on free multi-user online games with player IDs and a steady flow of tiny amounts for skins, weapons, extra time etc. using psychological techniques to keep players playing and paying.

It turns games into gambling and the near automatic result is addiction. Today mobile games measure an *individual* gamer’s thresholds for loss aversion, endowment/envy/embarrassment effects, susceptibility to scarcity perception live. They use this information to personalize the game, adjusting offers and prices accordingly, e.g. via ironSource technology purchased by Unity.

Vendors will argue that data collection and game individualization is necessary and their business model depends on it to make their services “better”.

They have started to turn the data collection not just into a business model for themselves, but also into a business model for the player-consumer having them gain staked digital assets from competing gamers via distributed ledger technologies (DLTs) (“play-to-earn”), blurring gaming and gambling, encouraging addiction.

This personalized content loop will spread from mobile games to wherever else it fits. We know the temptation to create addictive content is irresistible. So we can and must regulate before it happens.

- Measurement-based individual personalization needs to be heavily regulated or outright stopped via anti-addiction regulation, where service providers need to

prove their offers do not create addition, perhaps by proving that their revenues do not profit from addiction.

- These certifications need to be made externally and independently, similar to the food safety/building code approach.
- The residual risks and consequences need to be compensated with via regulated underwriting and insurance.
- Pay-to-win, play-to-earn schemes and loot boxes may need to be illegal from the outset, or at least have age restrictions or the financial exposure limited to fixed total amounts per individual and time period.

Summary

Digitalization is no longer new; the “disruptive moment” is far behind us. Governments and companies failing to align ground and cloud rules aren’t “supporting innovation”, they are simply negligent.

With digitalization reaching every aspect of citizens’ personal, professional, and political life, the clashes in values between geographies need to be anticipated and prepared for.

Events which from the EU look very remote and should only affect the poor residents of a US state with a dwindling population, can very easily have a global impact: righteous US judges and juries have no qualms coercing global cloud giants with a US base or connection into enforcing an ethos as controversial as refusing abortion to teenage rape victims on the planet. So far, we feel less pressure from Malta, an EU member with a similar stance, while France aims to make abortion a constitutional right.

China has long ignored criticism on its most egregious human rights transgressions within, and likewise refrained from imposing its doctrines to the general public outside its borders. But that might change about something as seemingly insignificant as a candy bar campaign mentioning “Taiwan” in the context of “country”[23]. This trend of having a very localized ethos overreaching far beyond “natural” borders via internet mechanics completely lacks compensating controls.

The digitalization of global interaction brings humanity into a contact that is far too close, immediate and unfiltered for comfort. Without the support of a spatiality⁹, which allows us to reuse the social code of civilization and diplomacy learned through centuries, millennia or even along our path to humanity and very much based on distance and visibility, we enter a phase where basic civility needs to be relearned, while our ability to inflict annoyance, anger or outright harm has been greatly enhanced.

The digital chasm is not just a technical problem or a short-term issue. It is a reboot of civilization with superpowers humans have not culturally evolved to manage properly.

That’s why we urgently need to deal with it with an urgency that fits the head-on collision we are trying to avoid.

For a start it requires essential international IT services like mobile play stores, games platforms, social media, payment services, security services must be split or pre-split at political borders that could foreseeably cause a disruption. We can’t allow a situation where domestic operations of a service are cut off because it’s delivered by a company that suddenly sits behind a new political wall. Businesses, agencies and consumers must know before they buy or contract, if a service can continue autonomously in a country or region like the EU. For critical services a local fallback must be provided and tested regularly.

References

- [1] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Great_Firewall
- [2] <https://www.semianalysis.com/p/china-and-usa-are-officially-at-economic>
- [3] <https://www.cato-unbound.org/2009/04/13/peter-thiel/education-libertarian/>
- [4] <https://www.debian.org/>
- [5] <https://lineageos.org/>
- [6] <https://www.linux-kvm.org/>
- [7] <https://www.mozilla.org/>
- [8] <https://www.libreoffice.org/>
- [9] <https://nextcloud.com/>
- [10] <https://www.sumatrapdfreader.org/>
- [11] <http://www.videolan.org/>
- [12] <https://www.thunderbird.net/>
- [13] <https://opnsense.org/>
- [14] <https://github.com/signalapp>
- [15] <https://virt-manager.org/>
- [16] <https://openvpn.net/>
- [17] <https://www.libreoffice.org/>
- [18] <https://nextcloud.com/>
- [19] https://www.theregister.com/2022/11/22/france_no_windows_google/
- [20] <https://www.opencompute.org/>
- [21] <https://www.heise.de/news/Nacktschanner-Unbedachte-Fotos-vom-Kind-fuer-den-Arzt-Google-Dienstes-gesperrt-7238900.html>
- [22] [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Steam_\(service\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Steam_(service))
- [23] <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2022-08-06/snickers-apologises-to-china-for-calling-taiwan-a-country/101308044>

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⁹ See the “Gaming, content and the metaverse” article in this HiPEAC Vision